

Safe and Explainable
Critical Embedded Systems based on AI

DS3.1 Automotive Safety Demonstration

Safe & Explainable AI for Pedestrian Emergency Braking

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1. System Architecture

- **Perception Node:** YOLO5-Tiny, Lane Detector, Overlay
- **Decision Node:** Rule-based fusion + VAE
- **Controller Node:** Braking logic
- **Supervision Node:** Monitoring + anomaly scoring
- **Supportive:** UI Visualization, Warning Sound, Lifecycle Managers

ROS2 DS-3.1 Autonomous Driving Architecture

2. Test Framework & Regulations (DS3.1)

- **Step 1:** Approach VRUs (adult, child)
- **Step 2:** Warning at TTW (≥ 0.8 s before braking)
- **Step 3:** Emergency braking at TTC AEB (≥ 5.0 m/s²)

- **Regulation:** UN R152 clauses 5.2.1.1 & 5.2.1.2
- **SOTIF:** Focus on AI perception limitations

2.2 SOTIF compliant Test Cases(TC's)

NODE	TC-ID	Description	Functionality Validated
Controller	TC1-0005	'Throttle pedal signal is wrongly provided to AEB due to low communication buses performances (e.g. busy buses, inadequate message priority or arbitration or EMI)	YES
Perception	TC1-0019	'Missing object detection due to camera low performances (e.g. damaged lens or undetected offline sensor)	YES
Perception	TC1-0020	Missing object detection due to short or long-term interference condition of the FOV (e.g. dirty window, water, ...)	YES
Supervision	TC1-0022	Too late detection of sensor decrease in performance (e.g. damaged lens, ageing effects, glare conditions, blockage condition of the FOV, extreme weather conditions, wrong camera position/camera calibration...)	YES
Supervision	TC1-0023	Too late detection of a collision relevant object due to inaccurate timestamp synchronization between the ECUs (e.g. object position is wrongly calculated)	YES
Controller	TC1-0024	The object is judged too late as collision relevant due to slow target vehicle's velocity calculation.	YES
Decision	TC1-0024	The object is judged too late as collision relevant due to slow target vehicle's velocity calculation.	YES
Decision	TC1-0025	The object is judged too late as collision relevant due to slow target vehicle's position calculation.	YES
Controller	TC1-0027	The object is judged too late as collision relevant due to slow target vehicle's acceleration calculation.	YES
Perception	TC1-0027	The object is judged too late as collision relevant due to slow target vehicle's acceleration calculation.	YES
Perception	TC2-0001	'Wrong object detection due to wrong camera position/camera calibration (e.g. the sensor is mounted in a wrong position/orientation so not-collision relevant objects could be exchanged as collision relevant)	YES
Decision	TC2-0009	The target object is wrongly detected as collision relevant due to incorrect object velocity calculation.	YES
Decision	TC2-0009	The target object is wrongly detected as collision relevant due to incorrect object velocity calculation.	YES
Perception	TC2-0010	'The target object is wrongly detected as collision relevant due to incorrect object acceleration calculation.	YES
Perception	TC4-0001	'Missing object detection due to camera low performances (e.g. damaged lens or undetected offline sensor)	YES
Supervision	TC4-0001	'Missing object detection due to camera low performances (e.g. damaged lens or undetected offline sensor)	YES
Controller	TC4-0014	'Missing object detection due to camera low performances (e.g. damaged lens or undetected offline sensor)	YES

3. AI & Compute Infrastructure

- **AI Modules:**
 - YOLOs-Tiny (pedestrian)
 - Lane Detector
 - VAE (uncertainty)
 - Rule-based logic

- **Execution Mapping:**
 - **GPU:** DL inference, GUI, anomaly detection
 - **CPU:** Decision, supervision, rule-based checks
 - **Middleware:** workload isolation, monitoring

3.1. Real-Time GUI

- **Visual outputs:**
 - Bounding boxes & detections
 - Confidence & anomaly scores
 - Time-to-Collision (TTC)
 - System warnings & brake requests

- **Overlay ensures explainability & debugging**

3.2. Overlay GUI functionalities (Pedestrian detection)

3.3. Overlay GUI functionalities (anomaly warning)

- As VAE doesn't do object detection, there is also no TTC. The Anomaly detected is the fountain on the roundabout

4. Demonstration Scope

- **Scenario:** Drive towards pedestrian
- **Conditions:** Day/Night, Dry/Wet, Adult/Child, 10-30-50 km/h
- **Extensions:** Fog, unseen traffic sign, hidden/slow pedestrian

- **Goal:** Warn driver + brake if no reaction

4.1 Test Automation & Analysis

- **Step 1:** ROSBAG → MCAP
- **Step 2:** Extract signals (objects, lanes, status, braking)
- **Step 3:** Automated Pass/Fail analysis
- **Step 4:** Reports + graphs

Note: we also do human validation of the failed scenarios

- **Coverage:** 24 scenarios × 5 runs + extras = 150 runs

Anomaly:

Event 1:

- Start offset: 54.75s since sim start
- Span: 1757403992.94s → 1757404005.06s ($\Delta = 12.12s$)
- Max anomaly score: 0.032
- anomaly_score: 0.0261
- Warning at: 1757403992.96s ($\Delta = 0.02s$)
- Brake at: 1757403992.96s ($\Delta = 0.02s$)

Pedestrian:

Event 1:

- Start offset: 42.84s since sim start
- Span: 1757403981.03s → 1757403983.52s ($\Delta = 2.50s$)
- Type Pedestrian confidence 0.98 distance 12.00m
- Warning at: 1757403982.06s ($\Delta = 1.03s$)
- Brake: **X** none
- Event OK (no brake/warning conflict)

Examples of graphs & textual output reflecting the anomaly and pedestrian detection in the selected scenario

4.2 Beyond the Test Matrix

- Extra scenarios tested: (visuals next slides)
 - Fog (low visibility)
 - Unseen traffic sign
 - Pedestrian crossing behind car
 - Slow pedestrian

- Validates robustness beyond DS3.1

4.2 Beyond the Test Matrix: Fog causing low-visibility

4.2 Beyond the Test Matrix: Caution Sign (Anomaly)

4.2 Beyond the Test Matrix: Pedestrian crossing behind a car

4.2 Beyond the Test Matrix: Slower Pedestrians

4.3 Live Demonstration

- **Runs:**
 - Realtime on ORIN, scenario: Day, Dry, Adult Pedestrian, 10 km/h
 - including warning sound
 - Replay on Foxglove of a MCAP on ORIN, scenario Day, Dry, Adult, 10km/h
 - Replay on Foxglove of a MCAP on ORIN, scenario Day, Wet, Child, 10km/h
 - Replay on Foxglove of a MCAP on ORIN, scenario of unseen traffic sign

Note: We will use the time available to demonstrate as much as possible

Live Demo

5. Conclusion of the AEB Demonstrator (Day vs. Night Performance)

- **Daylight & Dry Conditions**
 - Consistent and robust performance on lower speeds (10/30 km/h)
 - Timely detections and braking sequences
 - Generally compliant with DS3.1 criteria on lower speeds
 - Demonstrator sometimes not able to stop in time on higher speed (50 km/h)
- **Night & Wet Conditions**
 - Reduced sensor reliability and reflections
 - VAE sensitivity in the dark could be improved
 - Warnings and braking often simultaneous → minimal margins, occasional skids
- **Improvements**
 - **Perception:** low-light/wet dataset augmentation, glare reduction, radar/LiDAR fusion, TensorRT model
 - **Supervision:** adaptive anomaly thresholds, dual day/night calibration, uncertainty fusion
 - **Control:** friction-aware braking, predictive stopping distance, enforced warning–brake separation
 - **System:** latency budgeting, scenario-specific calibration

Thank you for your attention,
Questions?

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